

1 **Risk Analysis for Alien Taxa framework, adapted to South African NEMBA**
2 **A&IS Regulations (v.1.2)**

3
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14
15 **Version history**

16
17 v1.0: Kumschick, S., Wilson, J. R., Foxcroft, L.C. (2017) Guidelines for conducting
18 risk analyses under the NEM:BA Alien and Invasive Species Regulations of 2014.
19 Submitted to the South African Department of Environmental Affairs, March 2017.

20
21 v1.1: Kumschick, S.; Wilson, J.R.; Foxcroft, L.C. (2018) Framework and Guidelines
22 for Conducting Risk Analyses for Alien Species. Preprints 2018, 2018110551,
23 <http://dx.doi.org/10.20944/preprints201811.0551.v1>

24
25 v1.2 (and future version): to be available from Zenodo.

26
27
28 **Risk analysis framework**

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30 The questions are described here in detail. For each question, a section in the
31 Answer sheet needs to be filled in, generally consisting of Response, Confidence,
32 Comments/Rationale, and References. Unless otherwise stated, all these sections
33 need to be filled in. A glossary of terms used in the framework is provided in
34 Annexure S2.

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37 **1) Background**

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39 The background gives important information on the assessor, the *Area*, and the
40 *Taxon*.

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42 ***BAC1 Name of assessor(s)***

43 Give the full name and surname of the main assessor and any additional assessors. The lead
44 assessor takes responsibility for the assessment and is the author/assessor for correspondence. Add
45 more lines if more assessors were involved.

46
47 ***BAC2 Contact details of assessor(s)***

48 Add more lines if more assessors were involved.

49
50 ***BAC3 Name(s) and contact details of expert(s) consulted***

51 This can include internal (within same organisation or group of assessors) or external (including
52 international) experts or reviewers, which influenced, commented or amended the document before
53 submission. In the comments, outline the kind of contribution these experts made. Add additional lines
54 if several experts were consulted.

55

56 ***BAC4 Scientific name of Taxon under assessment***

57 The biological entity under consideration. The full scientific (binomial) name as well as taxonomic
58 authority is required. In most cases, this will be a species, but it could be another taxonomic level (e.g.
59 genus or sub-species). Mention the taxonomic level under comments. The organism under
60 assessment will be called the "*Taxon*" in the rest of the document. Check ITIS (<http://www.itis.gov/>) or
61 a taxon specific taxonomic database for the correct nomenclature, and note the validity of the name
62 under comments. Note in the references which database was used for the species
63 identification/name.

64

65 ***BAC5 Synonym(s) considered***

66 List synonyms of the scientific (Latin) name of the *Taxon* which were considered for this assessment.
67 Only list names included in the literature search, not synonyms which were not considered. Check for
68 synonyms in ITIS (<http://www.itis.gov/>) or a taxon specific taxonomic database. Note in the references
69 which database was considered.

70

71 ***BAC6 Common name(s) considered***

72 List common names of the *Taxon* which were considered for this assessment. Only list names
73 included in the literature search, not all recorded common names. In the comments, indicate where
74 the common names are used, and which languages were considered.

75

76 ***BAC7 What is the native range of the Taxon?***

77 The *Taxon's* biogeographic distribution provides useful context for understanding the actual and
78 potential range of the *Taxon*. Here, a description in words is required, which can aid the literature
79 search. If the *Taxon's* native range includes the *Area* or part of the *Area*, see BAC12.

80 A map of the native range should be provided, if possible. If the map is available in a file, please insert
81 a low res copy (<1MB) as an appendix to the Answer sheet and provide the file name and (if possible)
82 a link to a higher resolution copy.

83

84 ***BAC8 What is the global alien range of the Taxon?***

85 This includes the *Taxon's* global alien range, including the range within the *Area*. The distribution of
86 the *Taxon's* introduced range provides useful context for understanding the actual and potential range
87 of the *Taxon* and provides guidance for the literature search. For example, we are only interested in
88 negative impacts caused in the alien range for the impact scoring and classification, even though
89 some species also have undesirable effects in the native range under certain conditions.

90 A map of the alien range should be provided, if possible. If the map is available in a file, please insert
91 a low res copy (<1MB) as an appendix to the Answer sheet and provide the file name and (if possible)
92 a link to a higher resolution copy.

93

94 ***BAC9 Geographic scope = the Area under consideration***

95 Specify the geographic entity under consideration, i.e. the geographic scope of the assessment. In
96 most cases this will be the whole of South Africa, but can also be only a part of the country, for
97 example a single province, a national park or a river catchment. The region under assessment will
98 hereafter be referred to as the "*Area*". The *Taxon* should generally only be assessed in its alien range.

99

100 ***BAC10 Is the Taxon present in the Area?***

101 Note if the *Taxon* is present anywhere in the *Area*. In the case where the presence of the species is
102 not confirmed but a record has been noted, include field visits, as appropriate.

103

104 ***BAC11 Availability of physical specimen***

105 In the Response, state if a physical sample was collected in the *Area* (yes/no). The name of the
106 herbarium/museum and its accession number / record of the *Taxon* in the *Area* should be provided in
107 the respective section. The record should have been checked by a national and/or international

108 taxonomic expert, and the person at the herbarium/museum who identified the sample and date
109 should also be given.
110 If the *Taxon* has not previously been reported as present in the *Area* and the identity is not certain OR
111 if no herbarium or museum record is available, contact a relevant specialist. Record all information
112 that can be obtained from the specialist; including a reference to some herbarium or museum, so that
113 in the future if need be it will be possible to determine what the *Taxon*'s identity was compared to at
114 the initial identification, i.e. if it turns out in future that the identification could be wrong, we need to be
115 able to understand why it was identified as that particular *Taxon*.

116

117 ***BAC12 Is the Taxon native to the Area or part of the Area?***

118 Indicate whether the *Taxon* is native or alien and select one of the answers provided for each (yes,
119 no, or don't know). If native to parts of the *Area*, specify its native and alien range in the Comments. If
120 alien to the whole or parts of the *Area*, clarify under BAC7 that only alien ranges are considered for
121 this assessment. If the *Taxon* is native to the whole of the *Area*, it should not be considered for listing
122 under the NEMBA A&IS Regulations in that *Area* and does not go through the assessment process.
123 For species native to the mainland but alien on the off-shore islands, listing should only be considered
124 for the islands, i.e. the *Area* (as specified under BAC7) should be the islands.

125

126 ***BAC13 What is the Taxon's introduction status in the Area?***

127 If the *Taxon* is present in the *Area*, define its introduction status as follows (according to Blackburn et
128 al. 2011):

- 129 - alien in cultivation/captivity: individuals transported beyond the limits of its native range and in
130 captivity, quarantine or cultivation, i.e., individuals provided with conditions suitable for them, but
131 explicit measures of containment or explicit measures to prevent spread are in place
 - 132 - alien outside of cultivation/captivity: individuals transported beyond the limits of native range and
133 directly released into the new environment, or individuals escaped from cultivation/captivity, but
134 incapable of surviving for a significant period or, if surviving in the wild, no reproduction or, if
135 reproduction occurring, population not self-sustaining
 - 136 - established: individuals surviving outside of cultivation/captivity in locations where introduced,
137 reproduction occurring, and population self-sustaining
 - 138 - invasive: self-sustaining populations outside of cultivation/captivity with individuals surviving and
139 reproducing a significant distance from the original point of introduction, i.e. dispersal happening.
- 140 Give information on each step in the invasion continuum and select one of the answers provided for
141 each (yes, no, or don't know).

142

143 ***BAC14 Primary (introduction) pathways***

144 List historical, currently known and potential future entry pathways for the *Taxon* in the *Area* and other
145 introduced ranges. The pathway classification is based on the one accepted by the Convention on
146 Biological Diversity (CBD), (see also Essl et al. 2011). Provide information on all categories and, if
147 available, on the sub-categories in the Response.

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150 **2) Likelihood**

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152 This section deals with the likelihood of the *Taxon* to enter (LIK1 & LIK2), establish
153 (LIK3 & LIK4) and spread (LIK5 & LIK6) in the *Area*, which is representing the steps
154 alien taxa need to take in order to become invasive. This section therefore assesses
155 the likelihood of the *Taxon* to become invasive. The timeframe to be considered for
156 these questions is 10 years. In other words, we are assessing the likelihood of these
157 events to occur within the next 10 years.

158 All the answers are described in scenarios for each level separately, with each level
159 being an order of magnitude more likely than the next lower level. If the answer is
160 unknown, it is set as $p = 1$ due to the precautionary principle (i.e., a high likelihood is
161 assumed if not known).

162 Generally, all the answers in this section are structured in the same way, and they
163 follow the logic described here:

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- Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): as likely as winning the lottery if you play it once
- Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): as likely as a new person you meet having their birthday on the same day as yours
- Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): as likely as rolling 2 sixes when playing dice
- Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): as likely as getting heads when flipping a coin, i.e., fifty-fifty
- Probable ($p = 1$ for calculation purposes): more likely to happen than not

The probability levels p represent the likelihood of an event happening, and will be used to calculate a final likelihood of an invasion to occur (see Figure S2 and Table S2).

The questions in this section represent the invasion process, with two questions for each step in the process (i.e., entry, establishment, and spread). Each answer to the questions in this section is attached to a probability value p as indicated in brackets in the response options (i.e., Extremely unlikely: $p = 0.000001$; Very unlikely: $p = 0.0027$; Unlikely: $p = 0.027$; Fairly probable: $p = 0.5$; Probable: $p = 1$; Don't know: $p = 1$).

Figure S2 illustrates how to calculate a final Likelihood score from the answers provided in LIK1-LIK6. Subsequently, this value can be transcribed into a Likelihood description as in Table S2, which feeds into the Risk assessment (Table S3).

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Figure S2 The calculation of a final likelihood score from the likelihood questions LIK1-LIK6. The likelihood descriptions to extract a Risk score for the Risk assessment in Table S3 can then be found in Table S2.

Table S2: Transcription of Likelihood scores into descriptions for the Risk score in Table S3. The Likelihood score is calculated as in Figure S2.

Likelihood score	Likelihood (description)
$p \leq 0.000001$	Extremely unlikely
$0.000001 < p \leq 0.0027$	Very unlikely
$0.0027 < p \leq 0.027$	Unlikely
$0.027 < p \leq 0.5$	Fairly probable
$p > 0.5$	Probable

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LIK1 Likelihood of entry via unaided primary pathways

202 If the *Taxon* is present in the *Area* (see BAC10), the probability of entry should be set as 1. Still fill in
203 this section as if the *Taxon* was not present and give details on pathways, as this can inform risk
204 management and the feasibility to stop future immigration. However for the calculations, use the
205 probability of 1.
206 Estimate the probability that the *Taxon* enters the *Area* from outside the *Area* through unaided
207 pathways within the timespan of a decade. Consider the unaided pathways mentioned under BAC14.
208 Features of the *Taxon* which favour unaided entry include presence in neighbouring countries and
209 regions, water or wind dispersed propagules (e.g. floating propagules), the ability to fly long distances,
210 the ability for fish to move from one river catchment where introduced, to another via connected
211 waterways. Animal dispersal is also considered here, except domestic and farm animals which are
212 included under LIK2. The following factors can aid entry via animals: edible parts (e.g. fruits) which
213 are eaten by animals, propagules with spines/barbs/sticky substances which can attach to animals,
214 very small propagules which can get stuck in fur and feathers, pests attached to plants or animals.
215 List the pathways and corresponding likelihoods in the comments section. In the response, give the
216 highest likelihood for any pathway. The assessment should be based on the likelihood of entry based
217 on current and future pathways.

218

219 **Response options:**

220 Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): the *Taxon* and its propagules are highly sessile and are known
221 never to disperse on its own – proof is required for inability to move, otherwise classify as “Very
222 unlikely”.

223 Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): the *Taxon* and its propagules are sessile and do not usually disperse on
224 their own

225 Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): the *Taxon* is sessile, but it can disperse during one specific life stage, dispersal
226 capabilities are slow and short distance

227 Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): the *Taxon* is highly mobile during at least one of its life stages and can reach
228 a high dispersal capability during one of its life stages

229 Probable ($p = 1$): highly mobile *Taxon* with dispersal capability fast and over large distances

230 Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on the unaided pathways available to the *Taxon*

231

232 **LIK2 Likelihood of entry via human aided primary pathways**

233 If the *Taxon* is present in the *Area* (see BAC10), the probability of entry should be set as 1. Still fill in
234 this section as if the *Taxon* was not present and give details on pathways, as this can inform risk
235 management and the feasibility to stop future immigration. However for the calculations, use the
236 probability of 1.

237 Estimate the probability that the *Taxon* enters the *Area* from outside the *Area* through the pathways
238 mentioned under BAC14 which are human mediated (as opposed to unaided, which are covered in
239 LIK1) within the timespan of a decade. List the pathways and corresponding likelihoods in the
240 comments section. This also includes entry from neighbouring countries (consider it could in future be
241 introduced into neighbouring countries). In the response, give the highest likelihood for any pathway.
242 The assessment should be based on the likelihood of introductions based on current and future
243 pathways. For taxa which are already present in the *Area*, mainly focus on unintentional pathways.

244

245 **Response options:**

246 Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): There is currently no human aided entry pathway available/in use
247 for the *Taxon*, and no future pathway is expected to arise

248 Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): There is currently a human aided entry pathway available/in use, but the
249 *Taxon* is highly sensitive to movement and is unlikely to arrive alive at any life stage

250 Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): There is a human aided entry pathway available/in use which is infrequently
251 used, and/or future new pathways are expected to arise; also, the *Taxon* is not expected to
252 arrive in high numbers

253 Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): Several human aided entry pathways are available/in use but not regularly
254 used, and/or some potentially lead to a high number of introductions

255 Probable ($p = 1$): Several human aided entry pathways available and regularly used for the *Taxon*,
256 and high numbers of individuals expected.

257 Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on the human aided pathways used by the *Taxon*

258

259 **LIK3 Habitat suitability**

260 Indicate the likelihood of the *Taxon* to find suitable habitats in the *Area* for survival and reproduction.
261 Habitat includes the presence of suitable food items, hosts, pollinators, seed dispersers, and other
262 biotic conditions. If the *Area* encompasses multiple habitats, consider those that are most likely suited
263 and mention in the comments section which habitats were assessed. Thus also take the habitat
264 specificity of the *Taxon* into account. Artificial habitats include for example (with increasing degree of
265 artificiality) gardens, zoos, greenhouses, indoor habitats.

266
267 **Response options:**

268 Extremely unlikely ($p < 0.000001$): the *Taxon* is extremely specialised and there is no suitable habitat
269 in the *Area*, none of the key conditions for the *Taxon*'s survival are met

270 Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): the *Taxon* is highly specialised, but there is reason to assume that it might
271 adapt to some biotic habitat conditions; only highly artificial habitats which are rare or difficult to
272 maintain are suitable.

273 Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): the *Area* provides habitat that is only partly suitable to the *Taxon*; certain artificial
274 habitats are suitable

275 Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): the key conditions are met, but only in a marginal part of the *Area*; also non-
276 artificial habitats suitable.

277 Probable ($p = 1$): all key biotic habitat conditions are met in a large part of the *Area*.

278 Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on habitat requirements of the *Taxon*

279

280 **LIK4 Climate suitability**

281 Indicate the likelihood of the *Taxon* to find suitable climate in the *Area* for survival and reproduction.

282 Use the native and alien ranges as references for the *Taxon*'s distribution, as obtained in BAC7 and

283 BAC8. As a minimal standard, use published maps of climate zones to check whether the climate in
284 the *Area* is suitable for the *Taxon*. Such maps include the following:

285 - Koeppen-Geiger climate zones, updated by Peel et al. (2007)

286 - Richardson and Thuiller (2007) maps of global locations that match South African climates

287

288 Climate models are more desirable and lead to a higher confidence in the assessment.

289 If the *Area* encompasses multiple climate zones, consider those that are most likely suited and

290 mention in the comments section which climatic zones were assessed. For species already present in
291 the *Area*, the answer cannot be "extremely unlikely".

292

293 **Response options:**

294 Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): The *Area* provides no suitable climate (including artificially created
295 environments)

296 Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): The *Area* provides no suitable climate, but suitable climate can be
297 artificially created in small (<5%) parts of the *Area*.

298 Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): The *Area* provides little (<5%) climatic overlap with the known distribution of the
299 *Taxon*, excluding artificially created suitable habitats.

300 Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): The main climatic requirements are met in a marginal (>5% but <20% - one
301 fifth) part of the *Area*.

302 Probable ($p = 1$): The main climatic requirements are met in a larger part (>20%) of the *Area*.

303 Don't know ($p = 1$): no information is available on the climatic requirements of the *Taxon*

304

305 **LIK5 Unaided secondary (dispersal) pathways**

306 This includes the unaided pathways currently or potentially bringing the *Taxon* from the occupied

307 regions to elsewhere within the *Area*. It excludes unaided pathways bringing propagules from areas

308 outside of the *Area* into the *Area* (covered in LIK1). Indicate the probability that the *Taxon* disperses

309 naturally from a population within the *Area* to currently unoccupied regions and habitats. Mention

310 details of the expected dispersal pathways and mechanisms in the comments section. More precisely,

311 try to estimate the probability that the *Taxon* can disperse > 50 km in a decade. Features of the *Taxon*

312 which favour unaided dispersal include water or wind dispersed propagules (e.g. floating propagules),

313 the ability to fly long distances, the ability for fish to move from one river catchment where introduced,

314 to another via connected waterways. Animal dispersal is also considered here, except domestic and

315 farm animals which are included under LIK6. The following factors can aid dispersal by animals:

316 edible parts (e.g. fruits) which are eaten by animals, propagules with spines/barbs/sticky substances

317 which can attach to animals, very small propagules which can get stuck in fur and feathers, pests

318 attached to plants or animals.

319

- 320 **Response options:**
 321 Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): the *Taxon* and its propagules are highly sessile and are known
 322 never to disperse on their own – proof is required for inability to move, otherwise classify as
 323 “Very unlikely”.
 324 Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): the *Taxon* and its propagules are sessile and do not usually disperse on
 325 their own
 326 Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): the *Taxon* is sessile, but it can disperse during one specific life stage, dispersal
 327 capabilities are slow and short distance (< 50km in 10 years)
 328 Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): the *Taxon* is mobile and can reach a high dispersal capability during one of
 329 its life stages
 330 Probable ($p = 1$): highly mobile *Taxon* with dispersal capability fast and over large distances
 331 Don’t know ($p = 1$): no information is available on unaided dispersal pathways used by the *Taxon*
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333 **LIK6 Human aided secondary (dispersal) pathways**

334 This includes the human aided pathways currently or potentially bringing the *Taxon* from the occupied
 335 regions and habitats elsewhere within the *Area*. This question does not include dispersal from outside
 336 of the *Area* to the *Area* as this is covered in LIK2. Indicate the probability that the *Taxon* gets
 337 dispersed from a population within the *Area* to uninvaded habitats. Intentional and unintentional
 338 pathways need to be considered. Mention details of the expected pathways in the comments section.
 339 The likelihood score relates to the proximity of the *Taxon* to human and domestic/farm animals and
 340 frequency of contact, which allows it to be dispersed in these kinds of dispersal pathways, as well as
 341 traits and features of the *Taxon* which facilitate for it to be moved around.
 342 More precisely, try to estimate the probability that human-mediated dispersal takes (propagules of)
 343 the *Taxon* > 50 km in a decade.
 344 Features of the *Taxon* which favour human aided dispersal include edible parts (e.g. fruits),
 345 propagules with spines/barbs/sticky substances which can attach to clothing, vehicles and boats,
 346 building materials, very small propagules which can get stuck in clothing/shoes or with movement of
 347 ornamental plants and be transported unnoticed. Dispersal by domestic and farm animals is included
 348 here.

- 349
 350 **Response options:**
 351 Extremely unlikely ($p = 0.000001$): the *Taxon* is not present in places accessible by humans, domestic
 352 and/or farm animals
 353 Very unlikely ($p = 0.0027$): the *Taxon* is only present in places humans, domestic and/or farm animals
 354 can reach with difficulty, and/or has no features which make it likely to be dispersed human
 355 aided
 356 Unlikely ($p = 0.027$): the *Taxon* is present in places where humans, domestic and/or farm animals
 357 occasionally occur, and/or has features which make it possible to be dispersed human aided,
 358 but only exceptional cases
 359 Fairly probable ($p = 0.5$): the *Taxon* is present in places easily accessible by humans and/or it or its
 360 propagules are easily moved, i.e. it possesses some feature mentioned above
 361 Probable ($p = 1$): the *Taxon* is present in a place frequented by humans, and it or its propagules are
 362 easily and regularly moved due to features mentioned above
 363 Don’t know ($p = 1$): no information is available on the human aided pathways used by the *Taxon*
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367 **3) Consequences**

369 In this section, all evidence of impacts in the global alien range (including the *Area*)
 370 available for the *Taxon* needs to be collated and scored for environmental impacts
 371 and socio-economic impacts. Data on the impacts of the *Taxon* itself from the *Area*
 372 or other alien regions are the most desirable (CON1a)-k) and CON2a)-f)). Only if no
 373 data are available on the *Taxon* in any alien range globally should it be classified as
 374 Data Deficient (DD) under CON1 and CON2.

375 If this is the case, i.e. no data are available for the Taxon on impacts anywhere in its
 376 global alien range, look for data of congeners or other closely related species with
 377 similar life history traits and fill in CON3 and CON4.

378 Additionally consider data in the native range of the *Taxon*, and/or estimate the
 379 magnitude of impact possible for the *Taxon* in the *Area* based on biological,
 380 ecological and behavioural traits in CON5. This needs to be filled in regardless of
 381 whether information on CON1 and CON2 is available, but can lead to similar results
 382 if the impact of the *Taxon* has been well studied.

383 The environmental impact (CON1) is based on the Environmental Impact
 384 Classification of Alien Taxa (EICAT) system by Blackburn *et al.* (2014), Hawkins *et al.*
 385 *et al.* (2015), and the socio-economic rating (CON2) based partly on the Socio-
 386 Economic Impact Classification for Alien Taxa (SEICAT) by Bacher *et al.* (2017).
 387 For a measure of future potential and currently unrecorded impact of the *Taxon* in
 388 the *Area*, CON5 includes considerations on the *Taxon's* traits, behaviour and
 389 ecology and considers impacts recorded in the native range.

390
 391 Fill all results as described below from CON1-5 into Figure S3 below and in the
 392 answer sheet to calculate maximum impact levels for the *Taxon*. For the
 393 consequence score, the maximum impact level should be taken between all the
 394 impact measures (CON1-5). This impact level is then used to calculate the risk score
 395 as described in Table S3.

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 401 **Figure S3:** Consequences in terms of impact scores
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406 **CON1 Environmental impact**

407 The consequence assessment is based on the Environmental Impact Classification of Alien Taxa
 408 (EICAT) scheme. EICAT classifies taxa into minimal concern (MC), minor (MN), moderate (MO),
 409 major (MR), massive (MV) according to the magnitude of impact they cause. Detailed descriptions of
 410 all the impact levels are given in CON1a)-CON1k) below.

411 Fill in the Answer sheet for each of the mechanisms as described below (CON1a-CON1k). Then use
412 the scheme provided in Figure S3 to calculate the environmental impact score (CON1), which is
413 basically the maximum of all the mechanisms. Report on the maximum impact found in any of the
414 mechanisms for the global alien range in the Response for CON1, and the main mechanism affected
415 in the Rationale, but provide information on all the sectors and impact scores in CON1a)-CON1k),
416 including detailed information on the references used for the assessments. If impact assessments
417 have been conducted previously for the *Taxon* and are available in the literature, information can be
418 extracted from there and no detailed search is needed.
419 If no data on impact are available for the *Taxon* anywhere in the global alien range for any of the
420 mechanisms described, mark the *Taxon* as Data Deficient (DD) here and additionally fill in CON3, i.e.
421 consider information on closely related taxa.
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425 **CON1a Competition**
 426 What is the evidence in the global alien range of the *Taxon* for impact through competition?
 427 Does the *Taxon* compete with native taxa for resources (e.g. food, water, space), leading to
 428 deleterious impact on native taxa somewhere in its global alien range?
 429 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the
 430 Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 431

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)
Competition resulting in replacement or local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible	Competition resulting in local population extinction of at least one native taxon, but changes are reversible when the alien taxon is no longer present	Competition resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction	Competition affects performance of native individuals without decline of their populations	Negligible level of competition with native taxa; reduction of performance of native individuals is not detectable

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 434 **CON1b Predation**
 435 This consists of the *Taxon* preying on native taxa somewhere in its global alien range, and includes
 436 direct effects leading to deleterious impact on native taxa.
 437 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the
 438 Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 439

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)
Predation results in local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible	Predation results in local population extinction of at least one native taxon; reversible when the alien taxon is no longer present	Predation results in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction	The alien taxon preys on native taxa, without leading to a decline in their populations	Not applicable; predation on native taxa is classified at least as MN.

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 441
 442 **CON1c Hybridisation**
 443 The *Taxon* hybridises with native species somewhere in its global alien range, leading to deleterious
 444 impact on native species.
 445 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the
 446 Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 447

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)
Hybridisation between the alien taxon and native taxa leading to the loss of at least one pure native population (genomic extinction); pure native taxa cannot be recovered even if the alien and hybrids are no longer present	Hybridisation between the alien taxon and native taxa leading to the loss of at least one pure native population (genomic extinction); reversible when the alien taxon and hybrids are no longer present	Hybridisation between the alien taxon and native taxa is regularly observed in the wild; local decline of populations of at least one pure native taxon, but pure native taxa persist	Hybridisation between the alien taxon and native taxa is observed in the wild, but rare; no decline of pure local native populations	No hybridisation between the alien taxon and native taxa observed in the wild (prezygotic barriers), hybridisation with a native taxon is possible in captivity

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 449
 450 **CON1d Transmission of disease**
 451 The *Taxon* transmits diseases to native species somewhere in its global alien range, leading to
 452 deleterious impact on native species.

453 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the
 454 Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 455

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)
Transmission of disease to native taxa resulting in local extinction of at least one native taxon; changes are irreversible	Transmission of disease to native taxa resulting in local population extinction of at least one native taxon; reversible when the alien taxon is no longer present	Transmission of disease to native taxa resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction; disease is severely affecting native taxa, including mortality of individuals, and it has been found in native and alien co-occurring individuals (same time and space)	Transmission of disease to native taxa affects performance of native individuals without leading to a decline of their populations; alien taxon is a host of a disease which has also been detected in native taxa and affects the performance of native taxa	The alien taxon is a host or vector of a disease transmissible to native taxa but disease not detected in native taxa; reduction in performance of native individuals is not detectable

456
 457

CON1e Parasitism

458 The *Taxon* parasitizes native species somewhere in its global alien range, leading directly or indirectly
 459 (e.g. through apparent competition) to deleterious impact on natives.
 460

461 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the
 462 Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 463

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)
Parasites or pathogens directly result in local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible	Parasites or pathogens directly result in local population extinction of at least one native taxon, but changes are reversible when the alien taxon is no longer present	Parasites or pathogens directly result in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction	Parasites or pathogens directly affect performance of native individuals without decline of their populations	Negligible level of parasitism or disease incidence (pathogens) on native taxa, reduction in performance of native individuals is not detectable

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CON1f Poisoning/toxicity

467 The *Taxon* is toxic, or allergenic by ingestion somewhere in its global alien range, inhalation or
 468 contact to wildlife, or allelopathic to plants, leading to deleterious impact on native species.
 469

470 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the
 471 Response is Data Deficient (DD).

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)
The alien taxon is toxic/allergenic by ingestion, inhalation, or contact to wildlife or allelopathic to plants, resulting in local extinction of at least one native taxon; changes are irreversible	The alien taxon is toxic/allergenic by ingestion, inhalation, or contact to wildlife or allelopathic to plants, resulting in local population extinction of at least one native taxon, but changes are reversible when the alien taxon is removed	The alien taxon is toxic/allergenic by ingestion, inhalation, or contact to wildlife or allelopathic to plants, resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction	The alien taxon is toxic/allergenic by ingestion, inhalation, or contact to wildlife or allelopathic to plants, affecting performance of native individuals without decline of their populations	The alien taxon is toxic/allergenic/ allelopathic, but the level is very low, reduction of performance of native individuals is not detectable

472
 473

474 **CON1g Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance**
 475 The accumulation of individuals of the *Taxon* on wetted surfaces leads to deleterious impact on native
 476 species somewhere in its global alien range.
 477 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the
 478 Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 479

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)
Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance resulting in local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible	Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance resulting in local population extinction of at least one native taxon, but changes are reversible when the alien taxon is no longer present	Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinctions	Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance affects performance of native individuals without decline of their populations	Negligible level of bio-fouling or direct physical disturbance on native taxa; reduction in performance of native individuals is not detectable

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 482 **CON1h Grazing/herbivory/browsing**
 483 Grazing, herbivory or browsing by the *Taxon* leads to deleterious impact on native plant species
 484 somewhere in its global alien range.
 485 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the
 486 Response is Data Deficient (DD).

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)
Herbivory/grazing/browsing resulting in local extinction of one or several native taxa; changes are irreversible	Herbivory/grazing/browsing resulting in local population extinction of at least one native taxon, but changes are reversible when the alien taxon is no longer present	Herbivory/grazing/browsing resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction	Herbivory/grazing/browsing affects performance of individuals of native taxa without decline of their populations	Negligible level of herbivory/grazing/browsing on native taxa, reduction in performance of native taxa is not detectable

487
 488
 489 **CON1i Chemical, physical or structural impact on ecosystem**
 490 The *Taxon* causes changes to either: the chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics
 491 of the native environment; nutrient and/or water cycling; disturbance regimes; or natural succession,
 492 leading to deleterious impact on native species somewhere in the *Taxon's* global alien range.
 493 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the
 494 Response is Data Deficient (DD).
 495

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)
Changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient and water cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession, resulting in local extinction of at least one native taxon; changes are irreversible	Changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession, resulting in local extinction of at least one native species, changes are reversible when the alien taxon is no longer present	Changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession, resulting in a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction	Changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession detectable, affecting performance (e.g., growth, reproduction, defence, immunocompetence) of native individuals without	Small changes in chemical, physical, and/or structural biotope characteristics; or changes in nutrient cycling; or disturbance regimes; or changes in natural succession detectable, but no reduction of performance of native individuals

decline of their
populations

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498 **CON1k Indirect impacts through interactions with other species**

499 The *Taxon* interacts with other (native or alien) taxa, (e.g., through pollination, seed dispersal, habitat
500 modification, mesopredator release), facilitating deleterious impact on native species somewhere in
501 its global alien range.

502 Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the
503 Response is Data Deficient (DD).

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)
Interaction of an alien taxon with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g., pollination, seed dispersal, habitat modification, apparent competition) causing local extinction of one or several native taxa, leading to irreversible changes that would not have occurred in the absence of the alien taxon	Interaction of an alien taxon with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g., pollination, seed dispersal, habitat modification, apparent competition) causing local population extinction of at least one native taxon; changes are reversible but would not have occurred in the absence of the alien taxon	Interaction of an alien taxon with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g., pollination, seed dispersal, habitat modification, apparent competition) causing a decline of population size of at least one native taxon, but no local population extinction; impacts would not have occurred in the absence of the alien taxon	Interaction of an alien taxon with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g., pollination, seed dispersal, apparent competition) affecting individuals without decline of their populations; impacts would not have occurred in the absence of the alien taxon	Interaction of an alien taxon with other taxa leading to indirect impacts (e.g., pollination, seed dispersal, apparent competition) but reduction in performance of native individuals is not detectable

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506 **CON2 Socio-economic impact**

507 Assess the socio-economic impact of the *Taxon* in its global alien range (i.e. everywhere it has been
508 introduced outside of its native range). Perform a SEICAT assessment on the *Taxon* as described in
509 Bacher et al. 2017, and in CON2a) to CON2d) below. This concerns impacts on the following
510 constituents of human well-being:

- 511 (a) safety
- 512 (b) material and immaterial assets
- 513 (c) health
- 514 (d) social, spiritual and cultural relations

515
516 Fill in the Answer sheet for each of the constituents of human well-being (CON2a-CON2d), and use
517 Figure S3 to calculate the main socio-economic impact score. Report on the maximum impact found
518 in any of the constituents of human well-being and any alien range in the Response to CON2, and the
519 main sector affected in the Rationale, but provide information on all the sectors and impact scores in
520 CON2a)-2d), including detailed information on the references used for the assessments.

521 If no data on impact are available for the *Taxon* in any part of its alien range globally on any of the
522 sectors described below, mark the *Taxon* as Data Deficient (DD) here and additionally fill in CON4.

523
524

525 **CON2a Safety**

526 This concerns impacts on human well-being affecting activities related to safety, for example personal
527 safety, secure resource access, security from disasters. Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level
528 according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).

529

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Local disappearance of an activity from	Local disappearance of an activity from	Negative effects on well-being	Negative effect on peoples' well-being,	No deleterious impacts reported despite	There is no information to classify the taxon

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
all or part of the area invaded by the alien taxon affecting aspects of human safety. Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien taxon, due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions ("regime shift")	all or part of the area invaded by the alien taxon affecting aspects of human safety. Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien taxon. "Local disappearance" does not necessarily imply the disappearance of activities from the entire region assessed, but refers to the typical spatial scale over which social communities in the region are characterised (e.g. a human settlement)	leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out. Reductions in activity size can be due to various reasons, e.g. moving the activity to regions without the alien taxon or to other parts of the area less invaded by the alien taxon; partial abandonment of an activity without replacement by other activities; or switch to other activities while staying in the same area invaded by the alien taxon. Also, spatial displacement, abandonment or switch of activities does not increase human well-being compared to levels before the alien taxon invaded the region (no increase in opportunities due to the alien taxon)	such that the alien taxon makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people in an activity suffer regarding safety. Reductions of well-being can be detected through e.g. income loss, health problems, higher effort or expenses to participate in activities, increased difficulty in accessing goods, disruption of social activities, induction of fear, but no change in activity size is reported, i.e. the number of people participating in that activity remains the same	availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being. Taxa that have been evaluated under the SEICAT process but for which impacts have not been assessed in any study should not be classified in this category, but rather should be classified as data deficient	with respect to its impact, or insufficient time has elapsed since introduction for impacts to have become apparent

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CON2b Material and immaterial assets

This concerns impacts on human well-being affecting activities leading to changes in the availability and quality of material and immaterial assets, for example adequate livelihoods, sufficient nutritious food, shelter, access to goods. Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien taxon. Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien taxon,	Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien taxon. Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without	Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out. Reductions in activity size can be due to various	Negative effect on peoples' well-being, such that the alien taxon makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people in an activity suffer in at least	No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being. Taxa that have been evaluated under the SEICAT process but for	There is no information to classify the taxon with respect to its impact, or insufficient time has elapsed since introduction for impacts to have become apparent

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data (DD)	Deficient
due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions ("regime shift")	replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien taxon. "Local disappearance" does not necessarily imply the disappearance of activities from the entire region assessed, but refers to the typical spatial scale over which social communities in the region are characterised (e.g. a human settlement)	reasons, e.g. moving the activity to regions without the alien taxon or to other parts of the area less invaded by the alien taxon; partial abandonment of an activity without replacement by other activities; or switch to other activities while staying in the same area invaded by the alien taxon. Also, spatial displacement, abandonment or switch of activities does not increase human well-being compared to levels before the alien taxon invaded the region (no increase in opportunities due to the alien taxon)	one constituent of well-being (i.e. security; material and non-material assets; health; social, spiritual and cultural relations). Reductions of well-being can be detected through e.g. income loss, health problems, higher effort or expenses to participate in activities, increased difficulty in accessing goods, disruption of social activities, induction of fear, but no change in activity size is reported, i.e. the number of people participating in that activity remains the same	which impacts have not been assessed in any study should not be classified in this category, but rather should be classified as data deficient		

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CON2c Health

This includes impacts on human well-being affecting their health, including strength, feeling well, access to clean air and water. Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data (DD)	Deficient
Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien taxon. Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien taxon, due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions ("regime shift")	Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien taxon. Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien taxon. "Local	Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out. Reductions in activity size can be due to various reasons, e.g. moving the activity to regions without the alien taxon or to other parts of the area less invaded by the alien taxon; partial abandonment	Negative effect on peoples' well-being, such that the alien taxon makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people in an activity suffer in at least one constituent of well-being (i.e. security; material and non-material assets; health; social, spiritual and cultural relations). Reductions of well-being	No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being. Taxa that have been evaluated under the SEICAT process but for which impacts have not been assessed in any study should not be classified in this category, but rather should be classified as data deficient	There is no information to classify the taxon with respect to its impact, or insufficient time has elapsed since introduction for impacts to have become apparent	

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data (DD)	Deficient
	disappearance” does not necessarily imply the disappearance of activities from the entire region assessed, but refers to the typical spatial scale over which social communities in the region are characterised (e.g. a human settlement)	of an activity without replacement by other activities; or switch to other activities while staying in the same area invaded by the alien taxon. Also, spatial displacement, abandonment or switch of activities does not increase human well-being compared to levels before the alien taxon invaded the region (no increase in opportunities due to the alien taxon)	can be detected through e.g. income loss, health problems, higher effort or expenses to participate in activities, increased difficulty in accessing goods, disruption of social activities, induction of fear, but no change in activity size is reported, i.e. the number of people participating in that activity remains the same			

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CON2d Social, spiritual and cultural relations

This concerns impacts on human well-being affecting social, spiritual and cultural relations, for example social, spiritual and cultural practice, mutual respect, friendship. Classify the *Taxon* in an impact level according to the descriptions below. If no data is available, the Response is Data Deficient (DD).

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data (DD)	Deficient
Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien taxon. Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien taxon, due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions (“regime shift”)	Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien taxon. Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien taxon. “Local disappearance” does not necessarily imply the disappearance of activities from the entire region assessed, but refers to the typical spatial scale over which social	Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out. Reductions in activity size can be due to various reasons, e.g. moving the activity to regions without the alien taxon or to other parts of the area less invaded by the alien taxon; partial abandonment of an activity without replacement by other activities; or switch to other activities while staying in the same area invaded by the alien taxon. Also, spatial	Negative effect on peoples’ well-being, such that the alien taxon makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people in an activity suffer in at least one constituent of well-being (i.e. security; material and non-material assets; health; social, spiritual and cultural relations). Reductions of well-being can be detected through e.g. income loss, health problems, higher effort or expenses to participate in activities, increased difficulty in accessing goods,	No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being. Taxa that have been evaluated under the SEICAT process but for which impacts have not been assessed in any study should not be classified in this category, but rather should be classified as data deficient	There is no information to classify the taxon with respect to its impact, or insufficient time has elapsed since introduction for impacts to have become apparent	

Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)	Data Deficient (DD)
	communities in the region are characterised (e.g. a human settlement)	displacement, abandonment or switch of activities does not increase human well-being compared to levels before the alien taxon invaded the region (no increase in opportunities due to the alien taxon)	disruption of social activities, induction of fear, but no change in activity size is reported, i.e. the number of people participating in that activity remains the same		

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555

556 **CON3 Closely related taxons' environmental impact**

557 This section is only considered if the Response is Data Deficient (DD) in CON1.

558 Consider here data of congeners or other closely related taxa with similar life history traits and their
559 environmental impacts in their global alien range. In detail, perform a classification of impacts as
560 described in CON1a-CON1k for closely related and similar taxa. Note which taxa was/were
561 considered in the Rationale, and report on the details of the different impact mechanisms on the
562 Answer sheet. In the Response to CON3, note the maximum impact found in any mechanism.

563

564

565 **CON4 Closely related taxons' socio-economic impact**

566 This section is only considered if the Response is Data Deficient (DD) in CON2.

567 Consider here data of congeners or other closely related taxa with similar life history traits and their
568 socio-economic impacts in their global alien range. More specifically, perform a classification of
569 impacts as described in CON2a-CON2d for closely related and similar taxa. Note which taxa
570 was/were considered in the Rationale, and report on the details of the different sectors on the Answer
571 sheet. In the Response to CON4, note the maximum impact found on any sector.

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573

574 **CON5 Potential impact**

575 This is filled in for all taxa regardless of whether information on the other impact questions (CON1-4)
576 is available. Ideally, experiments should be performed on impacts of taxa for which no information is
577 available regarding consequences of invasions, but this is hardly feasible for all taxa. Therefore, if no
578 data is available on impacts in any introduced region of the *Taxon* and any closely related taxon, use
579 data from the native range of the *Taxon* and/or estimate the magnitude of impact possible for the
580 *Taxon* in the *Area* based on its life history traits and trait based models for other taxa.

581 In detail, estimate the potential of the *Taxon* to cause any impact in the magnitudes as described
582 under CON1 and CON2 in the *Area*, including impacts for which no evidence has been recorded yet.
583 Assume the *Taxon* is established and abundant in the *Area*, and consider the highest impact possible
584 under any of the mechanisms and to any sector. Here we consider the life history traits of the *Taxon*
585 which could lead to impact, including undesirable traits, as well as the recipient systems, meaning the
586 recipient habitat and community. In some cases, impacts caused in the native range can be useful
587 indicators of impact, for example impacts on agriculture.

588 Undesirable traits include (but do not exclusively consist of): produces spines, thorns or burrs,
589 allelopathic, parasitic, unpalatable to grazing animals, toxic to animals, host for recognised pests and
590 pathogens, causes allergies or is otherwise toxic to humans, creates a fire hazard in natural
591 ecosystems, grows on infertile soils, shade tolerant plant at some stage of its life cycle.

592 Also consider here feeding habits, novelty aspects, functional traits, and studies performed on other
593 groups and taxa considering trait-impact relationships.

594

Impact levels	Massive (MV)	Major (MR)	Moderate (MO)	Minor (MN)	Minimal Concern (MC)
Environmental impact	Causes local extinction of at least one native taxon (i.e., taxa vanish from communities at sites where they occurred before the alien arrived), which is irreversible; even if the alien taxon is no longer present the native taxon cannot recolonize the area	Causes local or sub-population extinction of at least one native taxon (i.e., taxa vanish from communities at sites where they occurred before the alien arrived); which is reversible if the alien taxon is no longer present	Causes population declines in at least one native taxon, but no local population extinctions	Causes reductions in individual performance (e.g., growth, reproduction, defence, immunocompetence), but no declines in local native population sizes	Negligible level of impacts; no reduction in performance (e.g., growth, reproduction, defence, immunocompetence) of individuals of native taxa
Socio-economic impact	Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien taxon. Change is likely to be permanent and irreversible for at least a decade after removal of the alien taxon, due to fundamental structural changes of socio-economic community or environmental conditions ("regime shift")	Local disappearance of an activity from all or part of the area invaded by the alien taxon. Collapse of the specific social activity, switch to other activities, or abandonment of activity without replacement, or emigration from region. Change is likely to be reversible within a decade after removal or control of the alien taxon.	Negative effects on well-being leading to changes in activity size, fewer people participating in an activity, but the activity is still carried out.	Negative effect on peoples' well-being, such that the alien taxon makes it difficult for people to participate in their normal activities. Individual people suffer in at least one constituent of well-being (i.e. security; material and non-material assets; health; social, spiritual and cultural relations).	No deleterious impacts reported despite availability of relevant studies with regard to its impact on human well-being
Potential impact	The <i>Taxon</i> is a transformer in its native range, has ecosystem engineering properties, or possesses other traits which suggest irreversible impacts on the community composition in the <i>Area</i> to occur. The <i>Taxon</i> is a pest of agricultural production in the native range and has the potential to cause irreversible losses of activities.	The <i>Taxon</i> has traits which suggest major impacts on native communities in the <i>Area</i> , but these impacts are likely to be reversible. The <i>Taxon</i> has traits which can lead to losses of activities.	The <i>Taxon</i> possesses several undesirable traits. Due to the traits of the <i>Taxon</i> and/or its behavior, it is expected to reduce population sizes of at least one native species, and/or human well-being leading to people changing their activities.	The <i>Taxon</i> does not possess any traits which could lead to effects on native species population sizes, but reduction in native individuals' performance is expected; and/or it could lead to loss in individual peoples' well-being and increased difficulties to perform normal activities. No changes to activity sizes.	Due to the traits of the <i>Taxon</i> no effect on native individuals' performance is expected. No effects on human well-being are expected. The <i>Taxon</i> does not possess any undesirable traits.

596 **Risk assessment**

597

598 The risk posed by an alien *Taxon* is the likelihood the *Taxon* will become an invader
599 and the consequences in terms of impact resulting from the introduction of the
600 *Taxon*. The Likelihood for the risk assessment is derived from LIK1-LIK6 as
601 described in Figure S2 and Table S2. Consequences are derived from CON1-CON5,
602 as summarised in Figure S3. Table S3 summarises how risk scores are derived from
603 Consequences and Likelihood.

604

605 If the risk of the *Taxon* to become a harmful invader is medium or high (according to
606 Table S3), the management options section needs to be assessed. If the risk is low,
607 the *Taxon* does not need to be listed but under certain circumstances could be
608 monitored in the region it occurs. The Risk assessment therefore provides the
609 evidence base for or against the listing of a *Taxon* under the NEMBA A&IS
610 Regulations, whereas the Risk management section helps to decide which listing
611 status could be considered (Figure S4).

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614

615 **4) Management**

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617 A decision on the listing *status*, i.e., whether a taxon should be listed as prohibited,
618 Category 1a, 1b, 2 or 3 as outlined in the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations, is not only
619 based on scientific evidence, but often relies on the value of the *Taxon*, besides
620 some inherent features which make it more or less difficult to control. Therefore, risk
621 management considerations describing whether and how risks can be managed
622 apply, including benefits (Table S4 and MAN questions).

623

624

625 ***MAN1 What is the feasibility to stop future immigration?***

626 Assess here if future immigration of the *Taxon* into the *Area* can be prevented. If the *Taxon* is already
627 present as an alien in the *Area* (see BAC10), this is needed to determine whether eradication is a
628 feasible goal. If the *Taxon* is not yet in the *Area* this determines whether prevention is a feasible goal.
629 Based on the pathways identified in BAC14 and the answers provided in LIK1 and LIK2, estimate the
630 feasibility to stop propagules from entering the *Area*.

631

632 High: The *Taxon* is introduced into the *Area* intentionally with pathways which are easy to regulate
633 and control.

634 Low: The *Taxon* is introduced into the *Area* unintentionally, for example as contaminant and
635 stowaway, and/or is present in neighbouring countries and areas and is entering the *Area* unaided.

636

637

638 ***MAN2 Benefits of the Taxon***

639 Taxa with significant benefits and significant costs are sometimes termed conflict species. The
640 benefits might be in terms of either socio-economy or the environment. Crucially the benefits of an
641 introduction are often spatially and temporally separated from the costs of an invasion. This section
642 (MAN2a & MAN2b) aims at assessing current socio-economic and environmental benefits to highlight
643 potential conflicts of interest. Stakeholders might need to be consulted to answer these questions
644 (see also Novoa et al. 2018). Summarise the current benefits using the maximum of both, socio-
645 economic and environmental benefits as outlines below. Keep in mind that conflicts are expected
646 especially if socio-economic benefits are significant. If relevant, mention potential benefits here, but
647 base your response on actual, current benefits.

648

649

650 **MAN2a Socio-economic benefits of the Taxon**

651 Socio-economic benefits, if appropriate, should be described to ensure an objectivity and recognition
652 of the services that may be provided by the *Taxon*. Under Rational and comments, list the benefits
653 and the significance of each. Include here if the *Taxon* is used for any of the following: as pet, in
654 horticulture, for fencing, shading, dune stabilisation, firewood, building material, hunting, fishing,
655 human food, animal feed and fodder, fabric production, etc. Benefits are rated as of high or low
656 significance, based on the criteria outlined below. Details of the benefits and why they are rated in the
657 respective level need to be provided in the Rationale.

658
659 High: Significant benefits are expected if the *Taxon* provides a service or makes an activity possible
660 which is not available without the *Taxon*, i.e., which is not provided by the native species in the
661 *Area*. Also covered here are services provided by the *Taxon* which are essential for security,
662 adequate livelihoods, sufficient nutritious food, access to clean air and water, and food.

663 Low: List benefits which can relatively easily be replaced by another (native or non-harmful alien)
664 taxon, for example pets, trees providing firewood, game for hunting, horticultural plants, trees for
665 shade, cacti for fencing. Depending on the size of the affected industry, conflicts are still possible
666 therefore it is important to outline these benefits regardless. Also covered here are services
667 provided by the *Taxon* which affect aspects of human well-being related to social, spiritual and
668 cultural relations, for example friendship and spiritual practices.

669

670

671 **MAN2b Environmental benefits of the Taxon**

672 Here, benefits to the natural environment and native species in the *Area* are assessed. Benefits are
673 rated as of high or low significance, based on the criteria outlined below. Details of the benefits and
674 why they are rated in the respective level need to be provided in the Rationale.

675

676 High: High benefits are expected if the *Taxon* provides a crucial habitat or food source to an
677 environment. These functions might be replaceable over time by native taxa, but it indicates that
678 current control would be detrimental to conservation or ecosystem functioning. Significant benefits
679 are also noted if the *Taxon* provides resources which are not or no longer available without the
680 *Taxon* present to native species, especially to rare, endemic or threatened species.

681 Low: Benefits to native species and ecosystems which can relatively easily be replaced by another
682 (native or non-harmful alien) taxon.

683

684

685 **MAN3 Ease of management**

686 Some invasions are notoriously difficult to control, and this influences both the decisions concerning
687 risk management and how the risks should be communicated. Values as described in MAN3a-MAN3d
688 are assigned for situations where the *Taxon* has been detected, not where it could be found, in the
689 *Area*. This is only relevant if the *Taxon* is present in the *Area* (BAC10). Provide detailed answers to
690 MAN3a-MAN3d in the Answer sheet and use Table S4 to calculate the ease of management, i.e. the
691 sum of the answers.

692

693 **Response options (after calculating sum in Table S4):**

694 >5: Difficult. Generally difficult to manage (e.g. specialist equipment or techniques are required /
695 multiple approaches are needed for control to be effective / management is an expensive
696 operation over several seasons)

697 3–5: Medium. Some aspects make it difficult to manage

698 <3: Easy. Management is relatively straightforward (e.g. can be achieved without substantial training
699 or repeated control efforts)

700

701

702 **MAN3a How accessible are populations?**

703 Rate how easily accessible the populations of the *Taxon* are in the *Area*. Base your response on the
704 most difficult to access. Moderately accessible will include regions that pose some operational
705 difficulty, but that might not necessarily require specialised teams (e.g. a riparian area), and private
706 gardens. To be rated as difficult to access, the *Taxon*'s distribution must involve at least some sites
707 that are very difficult to access (e.g. a ravine).

708
709 **Response options:**
710 0 for easy access
711 1 for moderately accessible
712 2 for difficult to access; or don't know

713
714
715 **MAN3b Is detectability critically time-dependent?**

716 Assess if the *Taxon* is easily detectable during the year (response: no) or if it is only detectable during
717 certain seasons or time-periods (response: yes). The objective of this question is to distinguish taxa
718 that are readily detectable throughout the year from those that might be detectable only for short
719 periods (e.g. following the production of new foliage or as dispersing adults). If the *Taxon* is
720 detectable relatively briefly it provides only small windows for control prior to reproductive events.

721
722 **Response options:**
723 0 for no
724 2 for yes; or don't know

725
726
727 **MAN3c Time to reproduction**

728 Assess the time the *Taxon* takes from being juvenile to a reproductive stage (e.g. for animals how
729 long does it take from being born to reproducing?). It will be more difficult to prevent reproduction of a
730 *Taxon* that reproduces quickly than those that have extended juvenile periods. Default value (i.e. if
731 unknown) is 1.

732
733 **Response options:**
734 0 for > 3 years
735 1 for 1–3 years; or don't know
736 2 for < 1 year

737
738
739 **MAN3d Propagule persistence**

740 Describe here how long resting stages, seeds, spores, fragments, eggs, or other parts of the *Taxon*
741 can stay/persist in an environment before they die and are not able to progress to adult stages.
742 Propagule persistence is often one of the most important impedance factors, since it sets the
743 minimum duration for an eradication programme. Default value if unknown is 1.

744
745 **Response options:**
746 0 for < 1 year
747 1 for 1–5 years; or don't know
748 3 for > 5 years

749
750
751 **MAN4 Has the feasibility of eradication been evaluated?**

752 Assess if an eradication feasibility study has been performed for the *Taxon* in the *Area* specifically.
753 Determining whether eradication is a feasible goal is a process in and of itself requires some of the
754 information that is used elsewhere in this framework [e.g. whether it is feasible to stop future
755 immigration (MAN1), and the overall ease of management (MAN3)], but also much more. Most of this
756 information will only become available as control effort are piloted (see Wilson et al. 2017 for detailed
757 guidelines for evaluating eradication feasibility and monitoring progress). A detailed evaluation of
758 eradication feasibility will at a minimum include: explicit delimitation of populations, trial management,
759 an assessment of current status, a risk map, a bioeconomic / decision support model showing costs
760 and potential success of different control scenarios (e.g. Moore et al. 2011), and a proposed
761 management strategy with time-lines and specific goals.

762 Given there is often a short temporal window during which eradication is feasible (and after which the
763 *Taxon* has become too widespread and numerous in the *Area*) it is important that control efforts are
764 not delayed until a regulatory decision has been finalised. Therefore, under this framework, a
765 recommendation is not dependent on whether the feasibility of eradication has been evaluated or not.

766 However, only if there has been a specific and detailed evaluation should eradication be set as the
 767 management goal in the regulations. If the pilot management achieves eradication before formal
 768 regulatory confirmation of an eradication attempt, then it will in no way limit future options (unlikely
 769 delaying eradication until it is too late).

770
 771 **Response options:**

772 Yes: there has been a detailed evaluation of eradication feasibility in the *Area* that has been
 773 documented (e.g. in a journal article).

774 No: there has been no evaluation of eradication or the evaluation is not detailed, or it is for a different
 775 region (i.e. not the *Area* for which the risk is analysed)

776
 777

778 **MAN5 Control options and monitoring approaches available for the Taxon**

779 Describe here management actions taken and control options available for the *Taxon*. If known, add
 780 information on eradication and control attempts in the *Area*, number of populations, distribution in
 781 hectares, and other information which can feed into control plans and/or eradication feasibility studies
 782 for the *Area*. Include measures taken in the *Area* currently and historically, and elsewhere. Include
 783 ongoing or future plans for biocontrol, herbicides registered, control trials, etc. Include information on
 784 the success of each method, if known. Use the following guidance based on the ones developed for
 785 the Global Invasive Species Database (GISD) and give more detail if known.

786 **Management goals and actions for alien taxa, adapted from GISD.**

Management goals	Definition	Actions / approaches
Prevention	Measures taken to stop the <i>Taxon</i> from entering the <i>Area</i>	Risk assessment Legal Status (restrictions) Best practises Cultural methods Management at port of departure Management of vectors Management at point of entry (e.g. at-border inspections)
Eradication	Actions taken to eliminate all occurrences of the <i>Taxon</i> from the <i>Area</i> . Long term, on-going eradication projects are included in this category.	(for eradication, containment, or impact reduction) Quarantine areas Inspection
Containment	Measures taken to stop or reduce the spread of the <i>Taxon</i>	Shooting Trapping
Impact reduction	Measures taken to reduce the <i>Taxon</i> or biomass (control), to keep the <i>Taxon</i> in a defined area (containment), and/or to reduce harmful effects of the <i>Taxon</i> (mitigation).	Hand removal Pesticides or herbicides Poisoning or toxicants Others (disease, fumigants, draining...) Physical-Mechanical (manual) Chemical Biological Cultural approaches Land management Utilisation Integrated methods
None	No management goal has been specified for the <i>Taxon</i> in the <i>Area</i>	NA
Unknown	It is not clear if a management goal has been set	NA

787
 788 Also consider the best methods to evaluate the distribution, expansion and/or density of the *Taxon*.
 789 These might include dedicated species-specific surveys; general surveys for invasions as part of
 790 atlassing projects; remote-sensing; and the collection of data using citizen science schemes (e.g.
 791 iNaturalist).

792
 793 **MAN6 Any other management considerations to highlight?**

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If yes fill in details of the consideration in appendix MAN6 (note the inclusion of an appendix is optional). These might include considerations of whether existing exemptions (e.g. for sterile cultivars or particular contexts) are appropriate or exemptions could be considered, and whether and what permit conditions might be appropriate. This is intended to support those tasked with decision making, so a critical evaluation of options (including those that are not suitable) is useful, but it should ideally be backed up with appropriate referencing. It might also include information useful for management prioritisation or that might ultimately end up in a species-specific management plan (and so not necessarily directly influence the wording in the regulatory lists).

Response options:

Yes: details are provided in appendix
No: no appendix is provided

5) Recommendations and reporting

Based on the information in the risk assessment and management sections, we consider several broad recommendations for the regulation of an alien *Taxon* (Figure S4). These differ based on whether the *Taxon* is already present in the *Area*, whether prevention or eradication are feasible management goals, and whether the *Taxon* has benefits to the *Area* such that it might be a conflict species that could be allowed under permit in certain conditions (Figure S4). Figure S4 describes how to arrive at certain recommendations for Risk management and listing from the answers provided in the Risk analysis.

For an easily digestible overview of the analysis, a summary sheet including the conclusions from each table should be provided, with short descriptions on the *Taxon* itself, impacts, risks, management options and benefits. An example is given in the Supplementary Material Appendix S3, based on the Reporting template in the Answer sheet. The full risk analysis with each question answered and all references, including detailed information on assessors, reviewers, *Taxon* and *Area*, and maps should be provided as well.

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Risk Analysis Report

(the following summary sheet is to be completed once all the other sections are completed, but will appear at the front of the report, keep to one page, and do not reduce the size of the text to get it to fit it. Please delete all this annotated text in brackets.)

Taxon: (as in BAC4)	Area: (as in BAC9)
Compiled by: (from BAC1)	Approved by: (leave empty)
Picture of Taxon	Alien distribution map (BAC8)
Risk Assessment summary: (Summarise here the answers to questions under section 2) LIK and section 3) CON, and from Table S3. Emphasise the situation in the Area, if such information is available, and distinguish information from elsewhere.)	
Management options summary: (Report on the main findings from section 4) MAN, which includes benefits and questions on the ease of control. Mention if an eradication feasibility study was done, or is recommended, and give some information on control options available.)	Risk score: (from Table S3)
Recommendations: (Outline the recommendation and reasons for arriving at this, i.e. why something came out as it did in the decision tree as presented in Figure S4. This should also include recommendations on further studies needed, management plans, stakeholder engagement, etc. Note what the current listing category is under the NEMBA A&IS Regulations and discuss if the recommendation is to change from this)	Ease of management: (Easy, Medium, Difficult)
	Listing under NEM:BA A&IS lists of 2014 as amended 2016: (check the regulations) Recommended listing category: (as in Figure S4)

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1. Background

BAC1 Name of assessor(s)	
Name of lead assessor	
Additional assessor (1)	
Additional assessor (2)	
BAC2 Contact details of assessor (s)	
Lead assessor	Organisational affiliation:
	email:
	Phone:
Additional assessor (1)	Organisational affiliation:
	email:
	Phone:
Additional assessor (2)	Organisational affiliation:
	email:
	Phone:
BAC3 Name(s) and contact details of expert(s) consulted	
Expert (1)	Name:
	email:
	Phone:
Expert (2)	Name:
	email:
	Phone:
Comments:	
BAC4 Scientific name of <i>Taxon</i> under assessment	
<i>Taxon</i> name:	Authority:
Comments:	
References:	
BAC5 Synonym(s) considered	
Synonyms:	
Comments:	
References:	
BAC6 Common name(s) considered	
Common names:	
Comments:	
References:	
BAC7 What is the native range of the <i>Taxon</i>? (add map in Appendix BAC7)	
Response:	Confidence:
Comments:	
References:	
BAC8 What is the global alien range of the <i>Taxon</i>? (add map in Appendix BAC8)	
Response:	Confidence:
Comments:	
References:	
BAC9 Geographic scope = the <i>Area</i> under consideration	
<i>Area</i> of assessment:	
Comments:	
BAC10 Is the <i>Taxon</i> present in the <i>Area</i>?	
Response:	Confidence:

Comments:		
References:		
BAC11 Availability of physical specimen		
Response:		Confidence in ID:
Herbarium or museum accession number:		
References:		
BAC12 Is the <i>Taxon</i> native to the <i>Area</i> or part of the <i>Area</i>?		
The <i>Taxon</i> is native to (part of) the <i>Area</i> .	Yes / No / Don't know	Confidence:
The <i>Taxon</i> is alien in (part of) the <i>Area</i> .	Yes / No / Don't know	Confidence:
Comments:		
References:		
BAC13 What is the <i>Taxon's</i> introduction status in the <i>Area</i>?		
The <i>Taxon</i> is in cultivation/containment.	Yes / No / Don't know	Confidence:
The <i>Taxon</i> is present outside of cultivation/containment.	Yes / No / Don't know	Confidence:
The <i>Taxon</i> has established/naturalised.	Yes / No / Don't know	Confidence:
The <i>Taxon</i> is invasive.	Yes / No / Don't know	Confidence:
Comments:		
References:		
BAC14 Primary (introduction) pathways		
Release		Confidence:
Escape		Confidence:
Contaminant		Confidence:
Stowaway		Confidence:
Corridor		Confidence:
Unaided		Confidence:
Comments:		
References:		

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887

888 **2. Likelihood**

889

LIK1 Likelihood of entry via unaided primary pathways	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

890

LIK2 Likelihood of entry via human aided primary pathways	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

891

LIK3 Habitat suitability	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

892

LIK4 Climate suitability	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

893

LIK5 Unaided secondary (dispersal) pathways	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

894

LIK6 Human aided secondary (dispersal) pathways	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

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3. Consequences

CON1 Environmental impact	
CON1a: Competition	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1b: Predation	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1c: Hybridisation	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1d: Transmission of disease	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1e: Parasitism	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1f: Poisoning/toxicity	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1g: Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1h: Grazing/herbivory/browsing	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1i: Chemical, physical or structural impact on ecosystem	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1k: Indirect impacts through interactions with other species	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON1 Maximum environmental impact (Figure S3)	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

900

CON2 Socio-economic impact	
CON2a: Safety	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON2b: Material and immaterial assets	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	

References:	
CON2c: Health	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON2d: Social, spiritual and cultural relations	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
CON2 Maximum socio-economic impact (Figure S3)	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

901

CON3 Closely related species' environmental impact	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

902

CON4 Closely related species' socio-economic impact	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

903

CON5 Potential impact	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

904

905

906 **4. Management**

907

MAN1 What is the feasibility to stop future immigration?	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

908

MAN2 Benefits of the Taxon	
MAN2a Socio-economic benefits of the <i>Taxon</i>	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
MAN2b Environmental benefits of the <i>Taxon</i>	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

909

MAN3 Ease of management	
MAN3a How accessible are populations?	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
MAN3b Is detectability critically time-dependent?	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
MAN3c Time to reproduction	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
MAN3d Propagule persistence	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
MAN3 Ease of management (SUM from Table S4)	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

910

MAN4 Has the feasibility of eradication been evaluated?	
Response:	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

911

MAN5 Control options and monitoring approaches available for the <i>Taxon</i>	
Response:	
References:	

912

MAN6 Any other management considerations to highlight? (if yes, fill in Appendix MAN6)	
Response	Yes / No

913

914
915 **5. Calculations**

916
917 **Likelihood =**
918 (fill in numbers in table below)

Parameter	Likelihood	Stages	Final assessment
LIK1		P(entry) =	P (invasion) =
LIK2			
LIK3		P(establishment) =	
LIK4			
LIK5		P (spread) =	
LIK6			

919
920 **Consequence =**
921 (fill in the responses)

Parameter	Mechanism/sector	Response
CON1a	Competition	
CON1b	Predation	
CON1c	Hybridisation	
CON1d	Disease transmission	
CON1e	Parasitism	
CON1f	Poisoning/toxicity	
CON1g	Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance	
CON1h	Grazing/herbivory/browsing	
CON1i	Chemical, physical, structural impact	
CON1k	Indirect impacts through interactions with other species	
CON1	Maximum environmental impact	
CON2a	Safety	
CON2b	Material and immaterial assets	
CON2c	Health	
CON2d	Social, spiritual and cultural relations	
CON2	Maximum socio-economic impact	
CON3	Environmental impact of closely related taxa (only score if CON1a-k are all DD, otherwise NA)	
CON4	Socio-economic impact of closely related taxa (only score if CON2a-g are all DD, otherwise NA)	
CON5	Potential impact based on traits, experiments, or models	

922
923 **Table S3: Risk score**
924 (highlight the respective fields)

		Consequences				
		MC	MN	MO	MR	MV
Likelihood	Extremely unlikely	low	low	low	medium	medium
	Very unlikely	low	low	low	medium	high
	Unlikely	low	low	medium	high	high
	Fairly probable	medium	medium	high	high	high
	Probable	medium	high	high	high	high

925
926 **Table S4: Ease of management**
927 (fill in numbers in table below)

Parameter	Question	Response ⁹²⁸
MAN3a	How accessible are populations?	929
MAN3b	Is detectability critically time-dependent?	930
MAN3c	Time to reproduction	931
MAN3d	Propagule persistence	932
MAN3	SUM	933

934 **Appendix BAC7:** Provide here a map of the native range, if possible. If the map is available in a file,
935 please insert a low res copy (<1MB) and provide the file name and (if possible) a link to a higher
936 resolution copy below.

937

938

939 **Appendix BAC8(a):** Provide here a map of the global alien range if possible. If the map is available in
940 a file, please insert a low res copy (<1MB) and provide the file name and (if possible) a link to a higher
941 resolution copy below.

942

943

944 **Appendix BAC8(b):** Provide here a map of the alien range in the *Area* if possible. If the map is
945 available in a file, please insert a low res copy (<1MB) and provide the file name and (if possible) a
946 link to a higher resolution copy below.

947

948

949 **Appendix MAN6:** An optional section, where other management considerations that might affect the
950 recommendations and that are not covered in MAN5 or elsewhere can be discussed. These might
951 include the potential for exemptions (of particular sexes, genotypes, phenotypes, or context), or of the
952 sorts of issues specific to the Taxon that would need to be considered under which permits might be
953 granted. Please include relevant references. This is not intended to be a section for broad
954 speculation, so if in doubt, leave out.

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Figure S4. A decision tree for determining the appropriate risk management response. The listing categories (1a, 1b, 2) are as per South Africa’s NEMBA A&IS Regulations.

960 **Annexure S2: Glossary**

961

962 **NEMBA A&IS Regulations:** The National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act
963 (NEMBA, Act 10 of 2004) Alien and Invasive Species Regulations (Department of
964 Environmental Affairs 2014)

965 **Alien taxon:** A taxon in a given area whose presence there is due to intentional or
966 accidental introduction as a result of human activity. Taxa that have part of their native
967 range in a given country, but whose presence in another part of the same country is
968 attributable to human actions that enabled the taxon to overcome fundamental
969 biogeographical barriers, are also referred to as alien here.

970 **Area:** The area of assessment for the risk analysis. Specify the geographic entity under
971 consideration, i.e. the geographic scope of the assessment. In most cases this will be
972 the whole of South Africa, but can also be only a part of the country, for example a
973 single province, a national park or a river catchment. The region under assessment will
974 be referred to as the Area in the framework.

975 **Extralimital:** A taxon that has part of their native range in a given country, but whose
976 presence in another part of the same country is attributable to human actions that
977 enabled the taxon to overcome fundamental biogeographical barriers

978 **Invasive taxon:** A taxon which is alien to an area and which has self-sustaining populations
979 there with propagules spreading from the initial site of introduction.

980 **Pathway:** The processes by which taxa are moved between areas.

981 **Primary (introduction) pathway:** The combined processes by which taxa are introduced
982 from one geographical location to another (cf. Vector). Classified into categories and sub-
983 categories.

984 **Propagule:** any spore, seed, fruit, fragment, or other part of an organism capable of
985 reproduction by sexual or asexual means

986 **Secondary (dispersal) pathway:** The processes by which taxa disperse or are dispersed
987 from one area of introduction to another.

988 **Risk analysis:** The process of identifying and assessing the likelihood and consequence of
989 an event, as well as considerations as to manage and communicate the risks.

990 **Risk assessment:** The process of evaluating the likelihood and consequence of an event
991 taking place. In this document, such an event would be an alien taxon becoming a
992 harmful invasive species. Risk assessment is part of risk analysis. Risk analysis is
993 comprised of risk assessment, risk management and risk communication.

994 **Risk management:** The process of assessing options by which the risks of an event (its
995 likelihood and/or consequence) can be reduced or mitigated.

996 **Introduction status:** Whether a taxon is found in an area to which it is not native (alien),
997 and how far along the introduction-naturalisation-invasion continuum it has reached.
998 Ideally as per the Blackburn et al. (2011) framework

999 **Vector:** A mechanism responsible for the transport of species to new areas where they did
1000 not previously occur. A pathway (for example shipping) could have several vectors
1001 associated with it (for example in cargo, in passenger luggage, on passengers or crew
1002 themselves, in ballast water, or attached to the hull).

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Appendix S3: Example of a reporting sheet for the risk analysis of *Psittacula krameri* in South Africa. Note this has been updated to the most recent format, and is slightly different from the approved version.

Taxon: <i>Psittacula krameri</i> (Scopoli 1769)		Area: South Africa	
Approved by: South African Alien Species Risk Analysis Review Panel on 18 May 2018			
Picture of Taxon (from https://www.rspb.org.uk/birds-and-wildlife/wildlife-guides/bird-a-z/ring-necked-parakeet/)		Global distribution map (from CABI)	
Risk Assessment summary: There is a high likelihood of entry, establishment and further spread in the Area where <i>Psittacula krameri</i> is already present in several locations. The environmental impact (i.e. on natural biodiversity) is moderate through competition with native species—there is room for more research in the Area as the information on impact was found elsewhere. Socio-economic impacts are moderate to major, given the situation in the native range and other alien ranges. This leads to a high risk.			Risk score: High
Management options summary: The benefits were rated as low as it is only used as a pet and has no other beneficial uses—however there is a substantial amount of breeding and trade around this species in the Area. The species could be replaced by another parrot species with less invasive tendencies. Management would be tricky as it is a charismatic species which is mainly present in urban areas. People like the species, and any control attempt will lead to a public outcry if not handled correctly. As a communally roosting species, it provides unique opportunities for control, and several methods are available.			Ease of management: Medium
Recommendations: Listing under the NEM:BA A&IS regulations as 1b is recommended, based on the high risk and relatively low benefits and the availability of many other, less invasive parrot species in the pet trade. Stakeholder engagement is crucial for any measures taken as it is a charismatic species and one of the most common pet birds. However, if it is allowed under permit conditions, i.e. listed as Category 2, it needs to be ensured that measures to prevent invasiveness and impacts are taken, also preventing the species' movement and reproduction, as it is hard to control the release and escape of this pet due to people's behaviour. Either way, an invasive species management programme must be developed in terms of section 75(4) of NEM:BA.			Listing under NEM:BA A&IS lists of 2014 as amended 2016: 2
			Recommended listing category: 1b

Suggested citation: SANBI (unpublished) Risk analysis of *Psittacula krameri* (Scopoli 1769) for South Africa as per the risk analysis of alien taxa framework v1.0, approved by the South African Alien Species Risk Analysis Review Panel on 18 May 2018, pp XX. (there is no doi for this report, but the link would be provided here in the general form <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.XXXX>)

Appendix S5: Guidance regarding the use of the confidence rating (taken from Hawkins et al. 2015, modified from the EPPO pest risk assessment decision support scheme (Alan MacLeod 09/03/2011; revised 28/04/2011; copied from CAPRA, version 2.74; 2)).

Confidence level	Examples
<p>High (approx. 90% chance of assessment being correct)</p>	<p>There is direct relevant observational evidence to support the assessment; <i>and</i> Impacts are recorded at the typical spatial scale over which original native communities can be characterized; <i>and</i> There are reliable/good quality data sources on impacts of the taxa; <i>and</i> The interpretation of data/information is straightforward; <i>and</i> Data/information are not controversial or contradictory.</p>
<p>Medium (approx. 65-75% chance of assessment being correct)</p>	<p>There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some information is inferred; <i>and/or</i> Impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which may not be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, but extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered reliable, or to embrace little uncertainty; <i>and/or</i> The interpretation of the data is to some extent ambiguous or contradictory.</p>
<p>Low (approx. 35% chance of assessment being correct)</p>	<p>There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment, e.g. only inferred data have been used as supporting evidence; <i>and/or</i> Impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which is unlikely to be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, and extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered unreliable or to embrace significant uncertainties. <i>and/or</i> Evidence is poor and difficult to interpret, e.g. because it is strongly ambiguous. <i>and/or</i> The information sources are considered to be of low quality or contain information that is unreliable.</p>
